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Wearable sensing for fitness and health

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Wearable Devices are Pervasive!

Ear-based Sensing

Instruments for Health Checks...

Apple announcement this week.

The image displays a collection of features for AirPods Pro, arranged in a grid-like layout. The central focus is a pair of white AirPods Pro in their charging case. Surrounding this are various feature tiles:

- Hearing Aid:** A large tile with a blue circular graphic and the text "Hearing Aid".
- Adaptive EQ:** A tile with a blue waveform icon and the text "Adaptive EQ".
- Effortless setup:** A tile showing a smartphone screen with "AirPods Pro" and "Connect" options, and the text "Effortless setup".
- Conversation Awareness:** A tile with a blue icon of two people and the text "Conversation Awareness".
- Conversation Boost:** A tile with a blue icon of a person and the text "Conversation Boost".
- Hearing Protection:** A tile with the text "Hearing Protection" and "On by default".
- Noise app:** A tile showing a bar chart with a green checkmark and "OK" and "49 dB", and the text "Noise app".
- Personalized hearing profile:** A tile with two AirPods and a blue waveform, and the text "Personalized hearing profile".
- Live Listen:** A tile with a blue microphone icon and the text "Live Listen".
- Hearing test results privately stored in the Health app:** A tile with a blue Apple logo and the text "Hearing test results privately stored in the Health app".
- Share results with doctor:** A tile with a blue clipboard icon and the text "Share results with doctor".
- Media Assist:** A tile with a blue ear icon and the text "Media Assist".
- Hearing Test:** A tile showing a smartphone screen with a blue circle and the text "Tap the Screen When You Hear a Tone" and "Hearing Test".

AirPods Pro gets hearing aid feature

On-Device In-Ear Microphone Sensing Systems

D. Ma, A. Ferlini, C. Mascolo. OESense: Employing Occlusion Effect for In-ear Human Motion Sensing. ACM MobiSys. June 2021.

Occlusion Effect

Hardware Prototypes over Time...

— Left Earbud
— Right Earbud
— In-air Mic

Walk

Activity Recognition: Head Movement has little effect on inner facing microphone

What can we do?

- Step Counting
- Gesture Recognition
- Activity Recognition
- User Identification
- Heart Rate Detection
- Respiration Rate Detection
- Running Coach
- Cardio-vascular and Respiratory Health

Performance

(a)

(b)

Step Counting Activity Recognition Gesture Recognition

Acc	w/o head move	300	72.76%	59.75%
	with head move	299	53.01%	29.55%
eMic	w/o music	109	67.68%	46.53%
	with music	208	52.47%	27.59%
OESense	w/o head move	300	91.26%	83.09%
	with head move	299	88.74%	79.62%
	w/o music	300	91.26%	83.09%
	with music	300	90.99%	81.15%

Activity recognition variability and personalization

Gait Recognition from In-Ear Microphone

(a)

(b)

Heartrate from In-Ear Microphone

Vital Signs while Running

Privacy and Efficiency

On Device Continual Learning and Training

LifeLearner: Hardware-Aware Meta Continual Learning System for Embedded Computing Platforms

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SenSys 23

TinyTrain: Resource-Aware Task-Adaptive Sparse Training of DNNs at the Data-Scarce Edge

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ICML 24

MCU (STM32H747I)

Prior Works & Limitations

Continual Learning (CL)

- Many labeled samples required
- High overheads of computation & memory

Meta CL

- Enables CL with a few samples (10-30) using meta-learning
- Low accuracy when many new classes are learned
- Meta CL incurs high resource overheads

Memory Overhead

LifeLearner: Latent Replay

Co-utilization of Meta-Learning and Rehearsal Strategy

LifeLearner's Architecture

LifeLearner: Lossless Compression

Observation: ~90% latent activations are 0

Hardware aware Implementation

- **Hardware-aware System Implementation**

Embedded Devices (Jetson Nano & Pi 3B+)

- Processor: ARM A57, A53
- RAM: 4GB, 1GB
- Development: PyTorch 1.8
- Backend Engine: QNNPACK

Microcontroller Units (STM32H747I)

- Processor: ARM M7
- SRAM: 0.5 MB
- Flash: 1 MB
- Development: TFLM, Lightweight Backpropagation Engine
- Backend Engine: CMSIS-NN, Eigen

Unique Hardware Characteristics of Microcontrollers

Flash (Storage) is read-only during run-time

Write operation on Flash is costly (if possible):

Feature extractor on the Flash and classifier in SRAM

Results

- LifeLearner is only **2.8% lower in accuracy** than **Oracle**
- LifeLearner achieves **11.4-178.7x smaller memory footprint** compared to **SOTA**
- LifeLearner **10% improvement over SOTA** and **63.8% lower end-to-end latency & energy** compared to Oracle

MCU Deployment

Employed MCUs
(STM32H747I)

Cortex-M7 Core Memory
SRAM: 0.5 MB
Storage: 1 MB

Dataset	System	Accuracy	SRAM	Flash	Latency	Energy
GSCv2	Backbone	-	81kB	475kB	956ms	218mJ
	Tiny ANML	0.209	181kB	738kB	968ms	223mJ
	Tiny LifeLearner	0.534	212kB	806kB	1160ms	271mJ

Tiny LifeLearner improves 32.5% accuracy with minimal resource overhead compared to Tiny ANML

Accuracy

LifeLearner falls short by **2.8% accuracy** compared to **Oracle**

(a) CIFAR-100

(b) MiniImageNet

(c) GSCv2

Thanks to:

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